

Success of Public-Private Partnership at Elementary School Level in Punjab (Pakistan)

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Abstract: The study was focused on, "Success of Public-Private Partnership at Elementary School Level in Punjab". Government in Punjab took on public-private partnership to offer educational facilities to poor and needy children. Beginning at Lahore in 1990 Punjab Education Foundation (PEF) became active and lively in 2004. The study was expected to answer the questions like (i) does PEF provide educational assistance for students of poor families living especially in slums? (ii) is there any increase in enrolment of students in elementary classes of PEF partner schools? and (iii) is PEF more concerned with Education For All (EFA)? Sample for the study was consisting of 25 PEF administration personnel, 29 PEF partner school administrative personnel and 222 teachers. Three types of questionnaires and interview schedules were designed as instruments for data collection. Major findings were that (i) PEF provides educational assistance for students of poor families living in slums. (ii) there is enrolment increase in elementary classes of PEF partner schools and (iii) PEF is partially concerned with education for all. Conclusions attained were that PEF is required to be reshaped into a revolutionized organization. Recommendations were that Punjab Education Foundation may be more concerned with EFA i.e. Education For All.

Keywords: Partnership, slums, enrolment, needy, assistance, revolutionized.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education policies in Pakistan were often prepared in accordance with the needs of people but could not be implemented properly and targets remained unattainable. Such like condition was ill-fate in a country of naturally rich mineral resources along with massively varied status of the land. Millennium Development Goals (mdgs) in education as per obligation of the state on international level remained unachieved and the public sector was seen ineffective in providing education for all. Status of the state remained inert in the list of developing countries of lowest degree of achievement in education. Factors behind this failure were many like time to time and spontaneous trial of policy ideas in education sector and implementing process. All such problems were required to be researched and resolved for future improvement in the system of education. Public-private partnership was required to be designed well and implemented in a balanced environment that would be helpful in attaining more efficiency in providing public services like water, sanitation, energy, transport, telecommunications, health care and education. Managing potential is shared to handle the risks properly between public and private entities. Public-private partnership was to be utilized as an instrument to deliver much needed infrastructure and services.

PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN EDUCATION IN PUNJAB

Punjab Education Foundation started to function in 1991. Onward from 2001 Punjab Education Foundation Act-XII of 2004 was passed in Punjab Provincial Assembly. It became lively for encouraging and supporting the private sector in providing education to the poor, through public-private partnership.

MISSION OF PUNJAB EDUCATION FOUNDATION (PEF, 2010)

“Promote quality education through public-private partnership, encourage and support the effort of private sector through technical and financial assistance, innovate and develop new instruments and enable private educational institutions to champion wider educational opportunities at affordable cost to the poor”. Latest figure indicates that male and female students as beneficiaries of PEF are 734,091(55.35%) and 591.956 (44.65%) respectively.

VISION OF PUNJAB EDUCATION FOUNDATION (PEF, 2010)

Promotion of an educated society through public-private partnership so that every child may have an equal access to the basic right of education in Punjab.

Archer et al (2002) pointed out the importance of the extent of retaining a sense of available education for the poor in the developing world. According to 2002 report for ActionAid concerned countries that in most of the areas the education systems were in a highly more terrible state of crisis than it is generally realized.

Emmett (Oxfam) (2006) reported that social inequality was the reality in the lives of people as public services were unavailable because of discouragingly expensive for the vast majority of poor people in developing countries but easily attainable for the needs of rich. Free of cost education, shelter and medical facilities for all humans are dreamt of but these services are not in the reach of poor people being in major population of developing part of the world while elite class being in minority enjoys all services fully and completely.

Government of Ireland (State Authorities, PPP Arrangements Act, 2002) defines that a partnership between public and private sectors to deliver a project or a service traditionally provided by the public sector is termed as public-private partnership while in return of cash value of the project or service the private sector becomes responsible, as per specifications of the public sector, for different elements like designing, building and financing the asset, operating and maintaining the asset, and providing a long term service relating to the asset and all that involves a risk transfer to the private sector, and allows the local authority to draw an economic and other resources not available otherwise.

Lowol (2003) analyzed that teacher education program becomes effective when it assures a deliverance of education leading to a reasonable confidence to both the teachers and their students while rectifying and solving their learning problems effectively and professionally.

Yusuf (2005) Emphasized upon introducing information and communication technology in teaching learning process that assures more efficient and productive education empowering it with a variety of tools enhancing and facilitating the teachers with professional activities.

Annan, K.(UN Secretary General) (2005) indicated in his report “In Larger Freedom” that the United Nations once was concerned only with governments of the world to achieve the prescribed goals for provision of services like shelter, health and education to their citizens but under present conditions peace and prosperity of the world is possible only with partnerships among governments, international organizations, the business community, active civil society and dynamic private sector that is assured with dependence on one other.

Robertson, H. J. (April 2003) indicated that public are termed as public because of an important purpose to be aimed at. Public means to serve a public good in the form of services. Corporations have created a misconception to convince Canadians to be overtaxed and blamed at large that education systems were inefficient and ineffective. Meanwhile unexpectedly corporations eagerly started new schools to establish and their investing target was the youth of nation. It was also exemplified the corporations with a fierce wolf underneath sheep’s clothing for public that might have surely visible. It was a clear motive of the private sector to follow a way to save and make money behind an interest of corporations in schools. It was convincingly concluded that private purposes and public purposes are identical against

the proper deliverance of services to unprivileged class and public private partnerships lead to disillusionment, dirty dealings and debt.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study focused upon success of public-private partnership at elementary school level in Punjab.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study attempted to answer the following questions:

- a. Does PEF provide educational assistance for students of poor families living especially in slums?
- b. Is there any increase in enrolment of students in elementary classes of PEF partner schools?
- c. Is PEF more concerned with EFA?

2. METHODOLOGY

The study was designed on a survey program of PEF partner school teachers, PEF partner school administration personnel and PEF administration personnel. That was related with Foundation Assisted Schools (FAS), New School Program (NSP) and Education Voucher Scheme (EVS) being run in Rawalpindi division through public-private partnership.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

Population of the study was consisting of PEF partner school teachers, PEF partner school administration and PEF administration. There are four districts as Attock, Chakwal, Jhelum, and Rawalpindi in Rawalpindi division.

TABLE 1: PEF PARTNER SCHOOLS RAWALPINDI DIVISION

Sr.No.	Name of District	FAS partner schools	NSP partner schools	EVS partner schools	PEF partner schools
1.	Attock	05	06	08	19
2.	Chakwal	36	01	08	45
3.	Jhelum	03	01	05	09
4.	Rawalpindi	09	09	15	33
	PEF partner schools Rawalpindi Division	53	17	36	106

SAMPLE OF STUDY

Population was distributed in three groups as PEF administration personnel, PEF partner school administration personnel, and PEF partner school teachers.

TABLE 2: SAMPLE OF STUDY

Sr.No.	Sample category	Population	selected	Sample	Sample percentage
a.	PEF administration	075		025	33.3%
b.	PEF partner school administration	106		029	27.4%
c.	PEF partner school teachers	848		222	26.2%

Sample of study was more than 25% of population selected in each category on stratified-random basis.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

Questionnaires were presented in a simple and easy form separately to PEF administration personnel, PEF partner school administration personnel and PEF partner school teachers. Interview questions were served to all PEF administration personnel, PEF partner school administration personnel and PEF partner school teachers.

DATA ANALYSIS

The collected data was tabulated and arranged appropriately in the form of variables, frequencies, percentages, score and means. Data obtained from the questionnaires was analyzed. Major findings were recorded. The conclusions emerged out.

In view of the research study the recommendations were also recorded. Main objectives of this study were to find whether (i) PEF was providing educational assistance to students of poor families living in slums, (ii) there was an enrolment increase in elementary classes of PEF partner schools and (iii) PEF remained more concerned with the target of Education for All. Cluster based sampling was formulated. Rawalpindi division consists of four districts as Attock, Chakwal, Jhelum, and Rawalpindi where 106 PEF partner schools are functional. Among those are 53 FAS, 17 NSP and 36 EVS partner schools. Present study was delimited to PEF partner schools in Rawalpindi division, concerned PEF administration personnel, PEF partner school administration personnel and PEF partner school teachers. Three types of questionnaires were designed. First questionnaire was for PEF administration personnel, second for PEF partner school administration personnel and third for PEF partner school teachers with 15, 19 and 11 opinion based statements respectively with five grades as Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Unconcerned (UC), Disagreed (DA), and Strongly Disagreed (SDA). At the end of each questionnaire three questions demanding three draw backs, three advantages and three suggestions were placed. Three types of interview questions were also formed as 6 questions for PEF administration, 16 questions for PEF partner school administration and 08 questions for PEF partner school teachers. Responding personnel were 25 of PEF administration personnel, 29 of PEF partner school administration personnel and 222 of PEF partner school teachers. Data was analyzed and interpreted by variables, frequencies, percentage, score and mean. All related contents were illustrated with the help of bar graph. Tabulation, analysis and interpretation of data were presented. Comparative analysis parameters are as follows;

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS PARAMETERS

TABLE 3: Public private partnership in elementary level of school education through pef provides educational assistance for students of poor families especially living in slums.

Variables	PEF administration	PEF partner school administration	PEF partner school teachers
SA	56.0%	31.0%	66.7%
A	44.0%	58.6%	31.9%
UC	0%	10.4%	1.4%
DA	0%	0%	0%
SDA	0%	0%	0%

Figure 1: PPP-PEF provides educational assistance for students of poor families

The above figure 1 evinces that 56.0% of PEF administration, 58.6 % of PEF partner school administration and 66.7 % of PEF partner school teachers were in favor of providing strong support, support, and strong support respectively for public private partnership through PEF provides educational assistance for deserving students of the poor families residing in slum areas.

TABLE 4: Increase in enrolment of students in elementary classes of PEF partner schools with public private partnership

Variables	PEF administration	PEF partner school administration	PEF partner school teachers
SA	44.0%	24.2%	41.4%
A	48.0%	44.8%	45.1%
UC	08.0%	24.1%	1.3%
DA	0%	6.9%	11.3%
SDA	0%	0%	0.9%

Figure 2: Increase in enrolment of students in elementary classes with PPP-PEF

The above figure 2 reflects that 48.0% of PEF administration, 44.8 % of PEF partner school administration and 45.1 % of PEF partner school teachers were in favor of providing support to the increase in enrolment of students in classes with public private partnership in elementary level of education.

TABLE 5: Regarding public private partnership through PEF being more concerned with EFA target achieving.

Variables	PEF administration	PEF partner school administration	PEF partner school teachers
SA	0%	27.6%	38.7%
A	20.0%	44.8%	31.5%
UC	32.0%	13.8%	18.5%
DA	48.0%	13.8%	11.3%
SDA	0%	0%	0%

Figure 3: PPP-PEF being more concerned with EFA target achieving.

The above figure 3 bears out 48.0% of PEF administration, 44.8 % of PEF partner school administration and 38.7 % of PEF partner school teachers were in favor of being disagreed, providing its support and strong support respectively to the public private partnership through PEF being more concerned with EFA target achieving in school locality.

3. FINDINGS

Major findings were that

- a) PEF provides educational assistance for students of poor families living especially in slums.
- b) There is an increase in enrolment of students in elementary classes of PEF partner schools. and
- c) PEF is partially concerned with education for all.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Conclusions came out of the findings are as below;

- a. PEF was providing educational assistance to students of poor families living especially in slums.
- b. There was an increase in enrolment of students in elementary classes of PEF partner schools and
- c. PEF remained more concerned with the target of Education For All.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Punjab Education Foundation is a luminous, prismatic and lively organization with public-private partnership in education especially in elementary school level. Findings attained from data analysis, and conclusions came into view gave rise to a few recommendations and those are hereby mentioned to renovate public-private partnership into a more innovatory program for education.

- i. PEF was providing educational assistance to students of poor families living especially in slums. Number of PEF partner schools are required to increase for the children of poor families to get education.
- ii. There was an increase in enrolment of students in elementary classes of PEF partner schools and that process may remain continued.
- iii. PEF remained partially concerned with the target of Education for All. It may remain more and more concerned till the achievement of target as that is the commitment of the state.

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